

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF HEMATURIA: CASE WITH PLACENTA PERCREATA

Ali Karakuş¹, Hasan Ekmen², Ali Bucak³, Orhan Delice⁴

Keywords

Hematuria,
Placenta percreata,
Perinatal mortality

ABSTRACT

Placenta percreata is very rare in the literature. It may be present with hematuria. Such a case was presented in this article.

INTRODUCTION

Placenta percreata is a placental implantation disorder that invades placental villi by penetrating the decidua layer to invade the myometrium, serosa, and peripheral organs. Placenta accreta is seen in 2,500 gestations. Of these, 75-80% are placenta accreta vera, 15-20% are placenta increta and 5% are placenta percreata.¹⁻⁴

CASE

A 35-year-old, 24-week-old pregnant patient presented to our clinic with a complaint of macroscopic hematuria continuing for two months. Her biography had a live birth with cesarean and two abortions. The patient was assessed at the emergency department and fitted with a probe. The consultation on obstetrics and urology was requested. In the ultrasonographic examination; a view of a live fetus in the intrauterine cavity, a large hematoma containing hypoechoic and cystic areas in place, completely filling the bladder was observed. Left lateral wall thickness increased and hyperechogenic appearance was interpreted in favor of hematoma in bilateral myometrium at cervical level.

The patient had irrigation of the bladder. The woman was admitted for follow-up by the delivery. She started bleeding again in the 8th hour. Ultrasonographic doppler were found to have no fetal heart beat and hematoma in the bladder. The patient was operated for emergency dilatation curettage. A patient with a bladder invasion was diagnosed with placenta percreata. The patient was discharged after two days of intensive care and five days of follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Macroscopic hematuria and bladder invasion are 25%. Massive maternal bleeding can occur. 9,5% maternal morbidity and 24% perinatal mortality. Increasing birth rates with zygotes may increase the incidence of placenta percreata. Placenta percreata should be considered a rare cause of hematuria. Definitive diagnosis can not be done with ultrasound. Magnetic resonance imaging can be

Volume: 1

Issue: 3

Page: 68-69

Received: 10.09.2025

Accepted: 01.12.2025

Available online: 12.12.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17903359

1-*Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Emergency Medicine, Hatay Türkiye, deniz@hotmail.com, 0000-0003-1358-3201

2-Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Emergency Medicine, Hatay Türkiye, dryol@hotmail.com, 0009-0005-8672-9920

3-*Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Emergency Hatay Türkiye, drkarakus@yahoo.com, ORCID iD : 0000-0003-4027-2193

4--Erzurum City Hospital, Emergency Medicine department, Erzurum, Türkiye, orhandelice@gmail.com, 0000-0003-1629-4245

performed. Depending on the number of infants in the treatment, uterine repair or hysterectomy may be performed.⁵⁻⁹

CONCLUSION

Rare placental anomalies should be considered in the definition of hematuria. Emergency surgery should be planned in these cases.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

Acknowledgements

No

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